

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FLEXURAL AND COMPRESSIVE STRENGTHS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL THERMOPLASTIC CFRP

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ABSTRACT

The unidirectional flexural failure of fiber reinforced plastics occurs directly beneath a loading nose of three- or four-point bending fixture on the compressive side of test specimen, especially in case of thermoplastic composites. The main reason is that the unidirectional compressive failure during flexural behavior is often influenced by shear and contact stress in the out-of-plane direction by loading noses. Therefore, the flexural fracture mechanism is complicated, and it becomes so difficult to evaluate the intrinsic flexural strength accurately. This study applied a specimen with waisted section between two loading noses of four-point bending test. The applied geometry was the same as that of the authors' proposed compressive test method. As a result, the proposed flexural test method has made an effect on verification of flexural fracture of thermoplastic CFRP and made it clear that the flexural strength has a strong correlation with the compressive strength with relation to fiber direction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite material (thermoplastic CFRP) whose matrix is a universally prevalent and comparatively low-cost plastics like polypropylene or polyamide has been expected to be applied to various engineering products including automobiles and airplanes because of its high mechanical and lightweight properties comparable to thermosetting CFRP [1].

The unidirectional compressive strength of CFRP is dominantly influenced by plastic kinking process that is caused by any initial local fibre misalignment and shear deformation [2,3]. This strength depends much on matrix's mechanical properties. In case of thermoplastic CFRP, the compressive strength in the fibre direction is much less than the tensile strength and plays a significant role for designing some robust materials and structures. The compressive-side failure might happen before the tensile-side failure under pure flexural moment. This may indicate some strong correlation between the compressive strength and flexural strength of thermoplastic CFRP. However, it is difficult to evaluate the intrinsic flexural strength of unidirectional CFRP owing to the stress concentration right under the loading nose during bending deformation.

In this study, the authors examined whether the proposed waisted-shape specimen whose geometries and dimensions were the same as the compressive one [3] could prevent the failure under the loading nose of four-point bending fixtures and the intrinsic pure flexural strength could be determined. A linear elastic numerical analysis was also carried out in order to compare stress distribution on the compressive surface of the proposed waisted specimen with that of the conventional rectangular cross-section beam under flexural deformation.

In addition to that, the relationship between compressive and flexural strengths under several temperature conditions was examined experimentally to investigate their failure mechanism.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

This study used two types of thermoplastic laminates manufactured through compression moulding by hot-press machine after stacked with several plies of continuous prepregs in a single direction. One of laminates was made from Tencate Cetex TC910 Carbon fiber / Polyamide 6 (PA6) unidirectional prepregs and the other was made from Toyobo Carbon fibre / acid-modified Polypropylene (a-PP) unidirectional prepregs. Specifications of both prepreg materials are indicated in Table 1.

Manufacturer	Tencate	Toyobo
Fiber	Carbon	Carbon
Matrix	PA 6	a-PP
Vf	43%	50%
Density	1.45 g/cm ³	1.35 g/cm ³
Width	166 mm	15 mm
Thickness	0.16 mm	0.08 mm

Table 1: Specifications of prepreg sheets.

2.2 Specimen and Configuration

Both compressive and flexural test specimens have the same shape with a waisted section in the central as is shown in Fig. 1. In the proposed compressive test method [3], the gripping area of the specimen was clamped directly by the hydraulic grips and the axial compression load was applied as shown in Fig.2. The compressive failure was located in the waisted area and the fiber-directional compressive strength caused by kinking deformation was accurately evaluated. The proposed flexural test method used on the four-point flexural fixture based on the standard ISO 14125 [4]. It is important to note that the two loading noses contact a specimen at where the width is constant as Fig. 3 indicates. All tests were carried out under the arbitrary-controlled temperature in a thermostat chamber.

Figure 1: Test specimen geometry.

Figure 2: Compressive loading configuration and failure behavior.

Figure 3: Flexural loading configuration.

And the proposed flexural test method used the same waisted specimen as proposed above and the same configuration as the four-point flexural fixture based on the standard ISO 14125 [4]. It was noted that the two loading noses were contact a specimen at non-waisted area as Fig. 3 indicates. All tests were carried out under the arbitrary-controlled temperature in a thermostat chamber.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS ON FLEXURAL STRESS

This section explains numerical finite element analytical methods for stress distribution on the compressive surface of unidirectional specimen under 4-point flexural deformation by conventional and proposed specimen's geometries.

Numerical simulation uses linear elastic parameters of unidirectional CF/PP composites as a representative. The anisotropic elastic parameters are indicated in Table 2. They were determined based on rule of mixture for composite materials. Fig.4 shows a 1/4 solid model of flexural test specimen and fixtures based on finite element method (FEM). The longitudinal direction of specimen is on the axis number 1 which corresponds to fiber direction. The 3D meshes and geometries of loading nose and support were defined as rigid body and the anisotropic elastic parameters in Table 2 were assigned into the specimen's 3D model. After numerical calculation until a maximum compressive stress at any point on the surface of specimen reaches the apparatus flexural strength of UD CF/PP which was about 800 MPa, simulated compressive stress and out-of-plane shear distributions on the 1 axis are analyzed and compared with relation to the conventional rectangular cross-section and the proposed waisted specimens.

Properties	Symbols	Input values [GPa]
Elastic modulus	E_1	110
	E_2	4.7
	E_3	4.7
	G_{12}	1.5
	G_{13}	1.5
	G_{23}	0.91
	Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}
ν_{13}		0.25
ν_{23}		0.59

Table 2: Linear elastic parameters of UD-CF/PP.

Figure 4: Four-point flexural testing 1/4 FEM model.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Simulation results

Fig.5 shows a simulation result indicating compressive stress and shear stress distributions along 1 direction on the compressive surface related to the conventional rectangular cross-section 4-point flexural test configuration. According to the standard, a flexural stress is evaluated to be 800 MPa between two loading noses as indicated in Fig.5. However, the fact is that maximum compressive stress is at a point where the loading nose contact, not between loading noses. This is clear from the experimental results. The actual failure is definitely located on the compressive side right under the loading noses even four-point bending test. This means that the evaluated flexural strength might be underestimated on the conventional rectangular cross-section specimen.

Fig.6 shows stress distributions simulated in case of the proposed waisted specimen. It is clear that the maximum stress on 1 axis is located around the center of the specimen not under the loading nose. The out-of-plane shear stress under the loading nose is less enough than the conventional case. These situations resulted in the failure at the waisted straight area as indicated in Fig.7. At that case, the flexural strength can be derived simply from the rectangular dimension of waisted area of the specimen independent of stress concentration by contact with loading nose. This might be close to the intrinsic compressive strength under flexural failure mode.

Figure 5: Stress distributions on rectangular cross-section specimen under flexural deformation.

Figure 6: Stress distributions on the proposed waisted specimen under flexural deformation.

Figure 7: Comparison of failure modes.

4.2 Failure modes

Failure morphology after the proposed compressive and flexural tests which used the same specimen configuration were observed by 3D X-ray CT system. Fig.8 shows the CT images of the out-of-plane cross-section of typical compressive and flexural fractures. Both specimens were tested at 25°C. The left hand side figure represents the compressive failure and the right hand side shows the flexural failure. The flexural failure caused compressive kinking mode as the pure compressive failure. Both kink band angles were almost the same as 30°. Then, the kinking deformation and buckling occurs even under flexural moment as well as axial compressive load. However, with relation to flexural kink band failure, the through-thickness stress has a gradient distribution so that there is tensile stress on the opposite surface. This behavior is quite different from the axial compressive test. This might lead to the complicated failure mode.

Figure 8: Comparison of failure modes at 13 cross-section view.

4.2 Comparison of strengths

Fig. 9 shows the relationship between compressive and flexural strengths, and test temperature. In all temperature conditions, the flexural strengths are about twice as much as the compressive strengths in both materials. Comparing the ratio of flexural to compressive strengths, CF/PA6 is a little higher than CF/PP. It is thought that the factor of the ratio is caused by the stress distribution under flexural moment in through-thickness direction. The authors examine the details of mechanism theoretically and quantitatively.

Figure 9: Relationships of flexural and compressive strengths.

5 SUMMARY

The intrinsic flexural strengths were evaluated appropriately by the proposed test method similar to the compressive case. Comparing the flexural and compressive strengths dependence on temperature, there were some strong correlations in case of both CF/PP and CF/PA6. Theoretical expression is required based on kink band failure mechanism.

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